

D1.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

WP1

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The ERMES Project

The EU defines an active implanted medical device (AIMD) as a device that relies on electrical energy or a source of energy other than that produced directly by the human body or gravity, intended to be implanted, into the human body. The modern demand for medical facilities, the burden of chronic diseases, and technological advancements are the major factors contributing to the growth of the use of AIMDs. The development of AIMD is limited by the restricted possibility of communication to either control or monitor their function being buried inside the body. ERMES project aims to develop a new concept for information transfer between medical doctors (MD) and AIMDs using synthetic molecular communication (MC). MC is a bioinspired communication strategy that involves the use of molecules to encode and transport information. ERMES aims to apply the concept of synthetic MC to enable medical doctors to communicate with future AIMDs. The researcher is going to involve: i) the selection and chemical design and synthesis of the suitable molecular messengers, ii) the design and validation of injection and modulation schemes for molecular messengers propagating in the body's vascular system allowing MD to communicate the desired information towards an AIMD, iii) the development of detection strategies for chemical messengers inside the bloodstream released by the AIMD, and the investigation of suitable concepts to ensure reliable and secure communication between the AIMD and MD. The ERMES will be organized to operate along four Pillars: 1) tools for the theoretical conception, consisting of analytical and simulation models for the design and optimization of all involved communication links, 2) in-vitro experimental systems on a laboratory scale for proofs-of-concept in a controllable environment, 3) in-vivo experimental systems based on models developed ad hoc for studies under real application conditions, 4) Trusted communication between AIMDs.

ERMES Consortium Members

Participant No. *	Participant organisation name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	UNIVERSITY OF CATANIA (UNICT)	Italy
2	INNOLABS SRL	Italy
3	FRIEDRICH-ALEXANDER-UNIVERSITAET ERLANGEN-NUERNBERG (FAU)	Germany
4	MICROFLUIDICS INNOV ATION CENTER (MIC)	France
5	UNIVERSITAET REGENSBURG (UREG)	Germany
6	TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE DEGGENDORF (THD)	Germany
7	BIONAVIS OY	Finland
8	AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR (AALTO)	Finland

Purpose of the document

The purpose of data collection within ERMES is to generate, organize, and preserve both experimental and theoretical data that underpin the development of synthetic molecular communication systems for Active Implanted Medical Devices (AIMDs). Accurate and systematic data collection will enable researchers to address the scientific and technological questions central to ERMES, including the design of molecular messengers, injection and modulation schemes, and receiver detection strategies. Furthermore, proper data management will facilitate reproducibility, cross-validation between consortium partners, and the possibility for other researchers to replicate and build upon the findings. In this way, ERMES ensures that the data lifecycle—from generation to long-term preservation—supports the project’s ambition of establishing a novel communication paradigm for AIMDs, while fully complying with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), EU data protection regulations (GDPR), and the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement.

Data Summary

The ERMES project will generate diverse datasets spanning simulation, experimental, and clinical-model domains. The data will be produced and curated across all Work Packages (WPs), reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of the project. Below is a summary of the main types of data expected from each WP:

WP1 – Coordination and Management

- **Data type:** Administrative, financial, and technical reporting data; project documentation; meeting minutes; deliverables; milestones tracking.
- **Format:** PDF, Word, Excel, internal project management platforms.
- **Purpose:** Ensure compliance with GA obligations, monitor progress, facilitate internal and external reporting.
- **Access:** Restricted to consortium and EC services.

WP2 – Communication Dissemination Exploitation

- **Data type:**, exploitation roadmaps, IPR documentation, mailing lists originating from newsletter subscriptions or registration to ERMES-hosted webinars.
- **Format:** PDF, PPTX, MP4, DOCX.
- **Purpose:** Dissemination to stakeholders, exploitation of results, IP management.
- **Access:** Some data public (open access), some restricted (confidential IPR-related documents).

WP3 – Communication-theoretical Modelling and Design

- **Data type:** Simulation results of molecular communication channels (diffusion models, advection–diffusion PDEs, stochastic simulations, information-theoretic analyses).
- **Format:** CSV, HDF5, MATLAB/Python scripts, LaTeX reports.
- **Purpose:** Provide quantitative predictions and design parameters for messenger molecules, injection schemes, and receiver detection.
- **Volume:** Medium to large datasets (GB scale, especially for stochastic simulations).

WP4 – Testbed for in-vitro MC

- **Data type:** Firmware codes of microfluidic instruments and experimental and experimental datasets from microfluidic platforms and testbeds, including optical/electrochemical signals, flow/pressure logs, and microscopy images.
- **Format:** C/C++, CSV, TIFF/PNG, proprietary instrument files (will be converted into open formats where possible).
- **Purpose:** Validate theoretical predictions under controlled lab conditions.
- **Volume:** Large image datasets and continuous sensor logs.

WP5 – Models of in-vivo MC

- **Data type:** Biological test data from egg CAM and rat models; video and imaging data (e.g., fluorescence microscopy, histology); physiological parameters during infusion tests.
- **Format:** TIFF, CSV, MP4 (video), SPR2, LSSF, LSMF and proprietary instrument files (will be converted into open formats where possible)..
- **Purpose:** Assess the feasibility of molecular communication in realistic biological environments.
- **Ethical note:** Data will be pseudonymized and handled according to EU and national regulations on animal research and data protection.

WP6 – Secure synthetic MC and ethical issues

- **Data type:** Raw and processed sensor data from receivers; machine learning training sets; classification outputs; error rates; cryptographic protocol test data.
- **Format:** CSV, JSON, Python notebooks, MATLAB files.
- **Purpose:** Develop and validate robust, selective, and secure decoding of chemical messenger signals.
- **Volume:** Medium to large.

FAIR data

In compliance with the European Commission guidelines, all data generated by the ERMES project will be managed according to the FAIR principles: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Data collection and curation practices will be designed to ensure proper indexing, metadata annotation, and preservation in trusted repositories. Decisions on data publication will take into account the balance between open science requirements and intellectual property (IP) protection. When results have potential for exploitation, priority will be given to securing appropriate protection (e.g., patent filing or other IPR measures) before making the associated datasets openly available. In all other cases, datasets will be deposited in open-access repositories, accompanied by rich metadata and clear licensing conditions, to maximize their reusability by the broader scientific community.

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Persistent identifiers

All ERMES data will be identified by persistent identifiers (PIDs). Whenever datasets are published in open repositories such as Zenodo, they will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). For specific data types deposited in public domain-specific repositories (e.g., imaging databases, chemical data resources), accession numbers provided by those repositories will be used.

Local and internal sharing

In addition to public repositories, a secure consortium-wide repository (e.g., OneDrive/SharePoint project folder) will be maintained for data not immediately released to the public. All internally shared files will follow a standardized naming convention and will be uniquely associated with descriptive metadata. This ensures that even pre-publication or confidential data remains findable and traceable among partners.

Naming convention

The unique identifiers (UIDs) for ERMES datasets will be composed of a structured hierarchy of standardized tags separated by underscores. The convention is as follows:

1. **Project tag (Tag01):** “ERMES” (identical for all UIDs).
2. **Reference Work Package (Tag02):** “WP1” to “WP6”.
3. **Datatype abbreviation (Tag03):** a 5-letter code plus a 3-digit incremental ID.

Ontology includes:

- “SIMUL” (simulation data),
- “CHEMX” (chemical/analytical data),
- “IMAGX” (imaging/microscopy data),

- “SENSR” (sensor/electronics data),
 - “INVOX” (in-vivo experiment data),
 - “OTHER” (other data types).
- Example: “SIMUL001”, “SENSR005”.

4. **Creation date (Tag04):** YYYYMMDD format (e.g., 20250510).
5. **Version (Tag05):** 3-digit incremental format “v001”, “v002”, etc.

Example UID

A dataset containing the first batch of in-vitro sensor signals generated under WP3, created on May 10, 2025, first version, would be named:

ERMES_WP3_SENSR001_20250510_v001.csv

This system guarantees internal traceability, version control, and alignment with FAIR requirements, while enabling straightforward mapping to public repositories once the data is released.

Making data accessible

Repository:

The chosen repository for all datasets and result outcomes is Zenodo [<https://zenodo.org/communities/ermes>], the open access platform managed by CERN for OpenAIRE. All datasets and records deposited in the Zenodo repository are automatically indexed in the EU Open Research Repository. As a result, ERMES datasets made available through Zenodo will also be visible and retrievable through the European Commission’s Participant Portal, ensuring long-term visibility and wide accessibility of project results, compliance with Horizon Europe Open Science policy.

Metadata:

The beneficiaries will ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications and to the related datasets arising from ERMES results. To comply with these obligations, beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights when publishing. Metadata of deposited publications and datasets will be openly available under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent. Metadata will be machine-actionable and include at least the following:

- publication details (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue);
- Horizon Europe funding acknowledgement (programme, project name, acronym, and grant number);
- licensing terms;
- persistent identifiers (DOI for the publication, authors, institutions, and grant);

- when applicable, persistent identifiers for datasets, software, or tools required to validate the conclusions of the publication.

A web database with a curated selection of data and metadata will be linked to the ERMES project website and maintained for at least four years beyond the project's end, ensuring dissemination, exploitation, and long-term accessibility for research and commercial uptake. All other data and metadata will be preserved through Zenodo and other trusted discipline-specific repositories, as long as they remain operational. The computational pipelines developed within ERMES will primarily rely on open-source software. Analysis scripts and workflows will be modular, well-documented, and released under a CC BY-NC license, to maximize reuse by both academic and industrial communities.

All project datasets will be stored in open, widely used formats (e.g., CSV, TXT, JSON, TIFF, PNG, MP4, PDF), ensuring long-term accessibility and compatibility with open-source tools (e.g., Python, R, Jupyter, ImageJ/Fiji, web browsers). Software required only for data reading (standard free tools) will not be considered part of the project outputs. This approach guarantees that ERMES research outputs—data, metadata, and software—will remain FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and reusable beyond the lifetime of the project.

Making data interoperable

Ensuring interoperability is essential for the reusability of ERMES data and for facilitating exchange across disciplines and platforms. To this end, the project will adopt standardized formats, metadata vocabularies, and ontologies broadly recognized by the scientific community.

- File formats: Data will be stored and shared in open or widely used formats, such as CSV, TXT, JSON (for numerical/log data), HDF5 (for large-scale simulations), TIFF/PNG (for imaging), MP4 (for video), and PDF (for reports). Proprietary formats generated by instruments will be converted into interoperable open formats whenever possible.
- Metadata standards: Metadata will comply with discipline-specific standards whenever suitable. For example:
 - Imaging datasets will follow the OME (Open Microscopy Environment) standards.
 - Chemical/analytical data will align with IUPAC nomenclature and JCAMP-DX formats.
 - Biological data will adopt ontologies such as MeSH (Medical Subject Headings) and NCBI Taxonomy.
 - Simulation and computational data will use structured metadata based on Dublin Core and OpenAIRE Guidelines.
- Ontologies and controlled vocabularies: The project will use established ontologies and controlled vocabularies to describe experimental conditions, molecular species, and communication schemes, ensuring consistent annotation and facilitating integration with external datasets.

- Repositories: Discipline-specific repositories inherently require the use of accepted metadata schemes. These will be adopted for relevant ERMES datasets, guaranteeing alignment with community practices.

By combining discipline-specific metadata with general FAIR-compliant standards, ERMES will ensure that all data are machine-actionable, interoperable, and reusable both within the consortium and by the broader scientific community.

Increase data re-use

The license selected by ERMES will be Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 (CC BY-NC 4.0).

- This license allows copying, distribution, and public communication of the work, as well as the creation and dissemination of derivative works.
- Reproduction, dissemination, and public communication are permitted only for non-commercial purposes.
- By uploading content, no transfer of ownership or property rights is implied: repository owners (e.g., Zenodo, domain-specific databases) do not acquire any rights beyond hosting.

All metadata will be licensed under CC0 (Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication), except for personal identifiers such as email addresses. Datasets will be made immediately available for re-use upon deposition in the chosen repository. In cases where intellectual property protection (e.g., patent filing) is sought, an embargo period may apply. In any case, datasets will be granted Open Access rights at the latest within 6 months after deposition. All deposited datasets will be openly available to third parties during the lifetime of the repositories. Standardized metadata and documentation will ensure that external users can easily validate, integrate, and build upon ERMES outputs.

Allocation of resources

The estimated article processing charge (APC) is on average €3,500 per publication. Each partner has its own fund for this purpose. These costs are eligible under Horizon Europe and will be covered by the authors and/or co-authors of the publications, according to the provisions of the ERMES Grant Agreement. Furthermore, ERMES beneficiaries are eligible to publish in Open Research Europe (ORE), the European Commission's open access publishing platform, which provides a rapid and cost-free route for dissemination. Whenever appropriate, authors will use this option to ensure timely, compliant, and zero-cost open access to ERMES scientific outputs.

Data security

All ERMES data files deposited in Zenodo are stored in CERN Data Centres. CERN has long-standing expertise in managing large-scale digital repositories and is committed to maintaining these infrastructures for the long term, hosting hundreds of petabytes of Large Hadron Collider data over the next decades. In the highly unlikely event that Zenodo ceases operations, CERN guarantees the migration of all content to other suitable repositories. Since all uploads are assigned Digital Object Identifiers, citations and external links to ERMES datasets will remain valid and unaffected by such transitions. For data not immediately suitable for open release (e.g., under temporary embargo or involving sensitive content), secure consortium-managed repositories (OneDrive) will be used, with access restricted to authorized partners only. Data transfer between partners will follow encrypted and secure communication protocols (e.g., SFTP, HTTPS, institutional VPNs), ensuring the protection of confidential and sensitive datasets during exchange. This approach guarantees long-term preservation, integrity, and security of all ERMES data, while ensuring compliance with FAIR principles, the Grant Agreement obligations, and relevant data protection regulations